

Speculation on One Dimensional Photon Reflection-Refraction and Newtonian Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 29, 2024

Reflection of particles is observed in Newtonian mechanics and Snell's law may be derived using Newtonian conservation of momentum parallel to the interface between two media with different indices of refraction.

In the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction, with the first medium being a vacuum, it may appear that Newtonian mechanics describes reflection. In such a case, it seems that a photon reflects from a molecule, but given the space between molecules, a photon also has the possibility of moving into the n_2 (index of refraction medium). Such a picture, however, seems to imply that further reflections should occur whereas the photon seems to move steadily, although with speed c/n_2 , in the second medium.

Furthermore, if one considers n_1 and n_2 as two media with indices of refraction close in value, it seems puzzling why a major reflection only occurs at the interface. We suggest that the importance of the n_1 - n_2 interface in this problem suggests something else. It is as if the junction is upsetting the motion and that reflection as well as refraction is needed on average to create a kind of balance or conservation whereas speed and p are not conserved as there is a change in forces at the interface.

In other words, we suggest that it seems that something more than simple reflection from a molecule occurs. In Newtonian mechanics, however, a particle is a point which is followed in x and t . It retains its velocity v and momentum unless acted on by a force, presumably at a point. It seems that such a scenario cannot describe one dimensional photon reflection-refraction.

The question then becomes: What should be the substitute? We suggest that the substitute viewpoint should be sensitive to an interface and not focused on impulse hits with molecules. In one region, n_1 , the speed is c/n_1 , while in the other c/n_2 . Thus, there is discontinuity in speed as well as in momentum p_{n_1} versus p_{n_2} , while energy is the same. We suggest that the presence of an interface breaks translational invariance and that a substitute viewpoint may be based on this idea.

For this to be the case, we suggest that there is a periodic x -dependent function associated with motion in each medium, which necessarily has repeatable units of fixed length. It is possible that the fixed length of the units differs from n_1 to n_2 . In other words, the function would be discontinuous at the interface, just as speed and momentum are. This would not be a problem if the function is associated with something that changes due to a force (like velocity and momentum), but if it is linked to a conserved quantity, for example, a kind of probability, then force cannot break conservation of this quantity as applied solely to the photon. This suggests a very different kind of motion than simple $x=ct$, but one which has repeatable units in x linked somehow to probability. Thus, we suggest that Newtonian mechanics cannot describe one dimensional photon reflection-refraction.

Newtonian Mechanics and Reflection-Refraction

Historically, there have been wave and particle viewpoints associated with light. A particle which is associated with a Newtonian mechanics viewpoint, can describe reflection and two dimensional Snell's law through the assumption of conservation of the component of momentum parallel to the interface between the two media, one with an index of refraction n_1 , and the other with n_2 .

In the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction, with $n_1=1$, i.e. a vacuum, it seems that a photon has a certain probability of receiving an impulse hit from a molecule at the n_1 - n_2 interface and reflecting. There is another probability for it to enter the space between molecules. A possible problem with this scenario is that it implies that there may be reflection throughout the medium n_2 , and that the reflected beam should somehow be composed of pieces from surface reflection and interior reflection. It seems, however, that experimentally reflection occurs at the interface. The idea of a simple impulse hit becomes less plausible if n_1 and n_2 are similar in value. In such a case, it is not clear, we argue, why there should be a large reflection only at the n_1 - n_2 interface when there are molecules everywhere.

The Case of Discontinuity

For one dimensional reflection-refraction, it is known experimentally that c/n_i is the speed in medium n_i and p_{ni} , its momentum, where p is the momentum in a vacuum. Thus, speed and momentum are discontinuous at the n_1 - n_2 medium interface. This is not a problem if the particle is a point which receives impulse hits at the interface. Thus, p and v (of the photon) are not conserved quantities if a force is present.

One may ask: What if there exists a conserved quantity which is not changed by the force at the interface? For example, energy is unchanged. It is a constant, however, and so with $E=pc$, changes in p and c cancel. What if there exists a conserved quantity in this problem which depends on p_{ni} ? In such a case, the important physics occurs at the n_1 - n_2 interface which seems to be the case experimentally.

The question then becomes: What is this conserved quantity? It is known that there is a probability a_1 for a photon to reflect and $1-a_1$ for it to refract AT the interface. Photon number is conserved.

It seems that for the interface to play a major role there should exist a periodic function of x with different wavelength values for different n_i . If this function is associated with conservation, it should be continuous at the n_1 - n_2 interface. In other words, motion is not smooth translation, from point to point. In fact, one may insist on continuity of the function and its first derivative as a start.

This scenario seems to be very different from Newtonian mechanics in that one has a fixed p_1 at each x in n_1 , but some function of x which differs for different x points within a wavelength. If one wishes to have action-reaction, a Newtonian idea, one could have a hump followed by a negative trough. On average, the bias of the hump would be cancelled by the bias of the trough, but locally there would be bias in the two regions of the wavelength. This suggests a somewhat complicated form of motion.

The question then becomes how to validate the above speculation. As is well known (1):

$1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract} \quad ((1))$

Writing: Probability = flux/ c (i.e. probability in terms of a number of particles) and using $E=pc$, one has:

$AAp_1 = BBp_1 + CCp_2$ where AA is incident flux, BB reflected and CC refracted ((2))

AA is used to indicate positivity of flux. Then as noted in previous notes, one may write ((2)) as as difference of squares which breaks into two equations which may be used to solve for B/A and C/A:

$A + B = C$ and $p_1A - p_1B = p_2C$ ((3))

If $A \rightarrow A \exp(ip_1x)$, then $d/dx A \exp(ip_1x) = Aip_1 \exp(ip_1x)$

so $\exp(ipx)$ may be the function of x described above. One may always set the interface at $x=0$, although this is not necessary to solve the problem.

At this point, we wish to consider why reflection and refraction must be considered together. If one assumes no reflection, i.e. $B=0$, then:

$A=C$ but $p_1A=p_2C$ which is a contradiction ((4))

Thus reflection does not occur simply because of an impulse (although a physical impulse is needed), but it is necessary to allow for the two continuity equations of ((3)). This is why it occurs at the n_1 - n_2 surface.

Thus, this non-Newtonian picture, which solves the problem of one dimensional photon reflection-refraction requires a conserved action-reaction motion in space with $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative being continuous because there are associated with some kind of conserved quantity which in this case is the square root of flux.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although reflection of bouncing balls etc occurs regularly in Newtonian mechanics and one may also explain Snell's law in two dimensions by using conservation of momentum parallel to the n_1 - n_2 interface, we suggest that Newtonian mechanics cannot solve the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem.

We note that in n_i (index of refraction), speed is c/n_i and momentum, p_{ni} , while energy is $E=p_{ni} c/n_i$. Thus, speed and momentum are discontinuous at an n_1 - n_2 interface. We note that reflection and refraction seem to occur at the interface and ask: What is so special about the interface that reflection occurs at this junction and not regularly at other points in space? We suggest that this must be due to a behaviour of the moving photon which is not disturbed by the

molecules of n_1 or the molecules of n_2 , but is particularly disturbed by the junction. If a particle is a point moving as $x=ct$, it is difficult to see any reason why the junction would be so special with respect to reflection. All that happens is that the molecules change. If, however, one has a periodic function in x , with different wavelengths in different n_i , and if this function is associated with a conserved quantity (unlike speed and momentum at the interface), one would expect the function and its first derivative at least to be continuous at the n_1 - n_2 junction. In other words, the junction is special because it breaks translational symmetry. This implies that motion is based on the wavelength regions and not point translation. In other words, one might imagine a kind of action-reaction in x with a crest followed by a trough within a wavelength to give an average semblance of smooth translation.

The question is whether the above speculation leads to a solution of the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem. We suggest that it does in that: $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$ may be written as: $AAp_1 = BBp_1 + CCp_2$ where AA is the incident flux, BB the reflected and CC , the refracted. Probability is taken as AA/c_1 , but $E=p_1c_1$ is used with $E_1=E_2$. One may then form a difference of squares and break the probability equation into two: $A+B=C$ and $Ap_1 - Bp_1 = Cp_2$. If one wishes the second equation to represent continuity of the first derivative, one may use an eigenvalue equation: $d/dx f(p,x) = p f(p,x)$ or $f(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$.

Thus, we suggest that one dimensional photon reflection-refraction is non-Newtonian.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change